

www.arseam.com

A PARADIGM MOVE TO MODERN HRM PRACTICES OF MNC'S- A STUDY

Pallavi Pahuja, Parinita Malhotra
Chandigarh Business school of administration ,
IKG PTU, Mohali, India

Abstract

Objective:

To view the unique and innovative HR practices of MNC's. To analyze whether the companies with innovative HR practices have satisfied/happy employees.

The study is the outcome and zest of accumulation of some illustrations of organizations having unique and innovative HR practices.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-

The present research paper is conceptualized and is based on secondary data collected from various resources like books, news papers, management journals and internet. In order to have a practical experience, this paper has also analyzed successful implementation of HR strategies at various organizations

Findings- Indeed there is a remarkable positive move of employers from being autocratic to democratic in nature. This remarkable and positive change in business environment has improved the work culture , employability and reduced attrition over the period of time.

With this move to modern HR practices, business houses have seen better productivity in employees. In many surveys conducted across the globe, Google and some more companies are awarded as best and top most employer's to work with .As, they have delighted employees. Undoubtedly , these companies are also epitome of success.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical examples of organizations following different HR strategies and also includes literature review about leadership and talent management, which promotes unique and interesting contributions in HRM research.

Key words: HR strategies, Modern HRM, Flexi work hours ,Job satisfaction, employee retention strategies.

Review of literature

Schuler (1992) in his study threw light on Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) has many different components, including policies, culture, values and practices. Strategic business needs of an organization are influenced by its internal (which mainly consist of factors such as organizational culture and nature of business) and external characteristics (consisting of the nature and state of economy in which the organization is existing and critical success factors, i. e., opportunities and threats provided by the industry), which are influenced by HR activities.

Thornhill, Lewis, Millmore, and Saunders (2000) found a potential role for HR-centred strategies to be used to change or realign the culture of an organization. An organization can change its culture through its recruitment strategy of replacing managers with those from outside, restructuring the organization, downsizing the workforce, training programmes, new reward strategies and performance management to alter employee behaviours or reinforce emergent ones. After the economic liberalization, Indian organizations were under pressure to change from low-cost, indigenous, less efficient and outdated technology to high-cost modern technology and prepare people to use it. This was done to develop and maintain their competitive edge in the larger business environment (Khan, 1999). The potential value of the employees is to be increased by collectively enhancing and linking their skills and capabilities in tune with the contemporary requirements of the market, and to be faster than the competitors. The success of the HRM will be determined by its ability to harness the intelligence and spirit of people by creating a learning climate. Indian organizations normally direct their HRM efforts towards the development of competencies, culture and effectiveness among employees individually or in groups

Organizations may use many mechanisms to achieve their HRM goals as without competent and committed employees, an organization can achieve very little even it has excellent technological and other resources at its command. Such an assertion gains better credibility in the context of developing countries like India, that is, typically in early growth stages in terms of economic development and growing more rapidly than the ,traditional‘ developed economies of Japan, North America and Europe. Hendry and Pettigrew (1992) propose that a number of internal factors such as the organizational culture, structure (positioning of HR), leadership, level of technology employed and business output directly contribute to forming the contents of HRM.

HRM could be seen as a menu of strategic choices to be made by human resource executives in order to promote the most effective ‘role behaviors’ that are consistent with the organization’s strategy and aligned with each other (Sparrow and Hilltrop, 1994).

Objectives of the research

- 1.) To view the unique and innovative HR practices of MNC’s
- 2.) To analyze whether the companies with innovative HR practices have satisfied/happy employees.

Research methodology

Secondary data is the basis of study

Sample of 5 companies has been taken, which shows unique HRM practices of these organizations.

Analysis

Google

Consistently , ranked as the best employer to work with, The Google has mastered the art of innovation in the field of HRM. The following reasons have made google , the best employer to work with.

- Google employees are self-motivated by the fact that ,whatever they create will benefit someone, and will make the employee happy.
- **Employee benefits:** The extension of paid paternity leave from seven to 12 weeks. New dads and adoptive parents working at Google can now take up to 12 weeks of paid paternity leave, while moms continue to be entitled to 22 weeks. "Not only is the policy generous, but the atmosphere at Google is such that you can take the full leave and not hurt your career,"
- **Genius" co-workers**
Another reason Google employees love their jobs is that they get to work with "genius" co-workers,
"The company attracts some of the best talent and best people to work with in the world, which is the most important bit," wrote a San Francisco-based Google program manager.
- **Unparalleled career opportunities**
"Opportunities for career growth, and tons of career development resources available," wrote a Google strategic partner development manager in Mountain View.

Phillips

No parking? Work from home at Phillips

Electronics firm Philips, lets employees who drive to work and don't get parking, go back and work from home. The logic: logging in from home is quicker than finding parking. Employees can choose to reach between 8 am and 1 pm. "When we are aware of road diversions and blocks and advisories about traffic disruptions, employees have the freedom to work from home and head out once the traffic restrictions have eased,"

Employee of Philips said.

SAP Labs: Come and leave when you want

Bengaluru's SAP Labs doesn't monitor entry and exit timings — employees decide when to get to work and leave. SAP allows employees to work from home once a week, a frequency that can be increased by their reporting managers. "It's about output and not how many hours the employees spend on work," a spokesperson for SAP Labs said.

. PricewaterhouseCoopers India has an employee friendly location

When PricewaterhouseCoopers India decided to open its third office in Mumbai, it chose the city's western suburb of Goregaon. In the National Capital region, the global consultancy firm is identifying a location at Noida. "At the end of the day, we want our employees to maintain a work-life balance. Otherwise, it will impact their productivity," PwC India human capital leader Jagjit Singh said.

Coca Cola: flexi work hours

The local units of Coca-Cola and Sapient have introduced flexi work hours that help employees avoid rush-hour traffic. "We start 30 minutes early at 8:30 am and close by 5:15 pm in order to beat the peak traffic hours," said Sameer Wadhawan, Vice President for Human Resources & Services at Coca-Cola.

Conclusion

- 1.) Indeed there is a remarkable positive move of employers from being autocratic to democratic in nature. This remarkable and positive change in business environment has improved the work culture , employability and reduced attrition over the period of time.
- 2.) With this move to modern HR practices, business houses have seen better productivity in employees. In many surveys conducted across the globe, Google and some more companies are awrded as best and top most employer's to work with .As, they have delighted employees.

Undoubtedly , these companies are also epitome of success.

Bibliography

ASHFORD, S. J.; CUMMINGS, L. L. 1983. Feedback as an individual resource: Personal strategies of creating information. *Organizational Behavior and Human Relations*.

BULLA, D. N.; SCOTT. 1994. Manpower requirements forecasting: a case example, in *Human*.
CARROLL, D. T. 1983. A disappointing search for excellence. *Harvard Business Review*. 1983, vol. 61, no. 6, s. 78–88.

CHATMAN, J. A. 1991. Matching people and organizations: Selection and socialization in public accounting firms. *Administrative Science Quarterly*. 1991, vol. 36, s. 459–484.

CUMMINGS, L. L. 1973. A field experimental study of the effects of two performance appraisal systems. *Personnel Psychology*. 1973, vol. 26, s. 489–502.

GUEST, D.; CONWAY, N.; BRINER, R.; DICKMAN, M. 1996. The state of psychological contract in employment: Issues in people management. London : Institute of Personnel and Development,